

EDEN ISS

D 7.10 - Dissemination Plan

prepared for

WP 7.1 - Public Engagement

Version: 1.0

Published: 2015-07-07

Approved by:	Barbara Imhof	LSG	Work Package Leader
Approved by:	Matthew Bamsey	DLR	Systems Engineer
Approved by:	Daniel Schubert	DLR	Project Manager

List of Authors:

Participant No.	Short name	Author name(s)
2	LSG	M. Hogle
1	DLR	P. Zabel, M. Bamsey, D. Schubert

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
1.0	2015-07-07	M. Hogle, P. Zabel, M. Bamsey, D. Schubert	Initial document

Executive summary

The dissemination plan (D7.10) is part of WP7.1 Public Engagement of the EDEN ISS project. It describes the various means and tools that will be used by the EDEN ISS team to not only reach out to experts and professionals, but also to the wider public, industry and stakeholders at large in the communication of project progress and results.

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Table of contents	4
Acronyms	5
1 Introduction	6
1.1 Overall Objectives of the EDEN ISS Project	6
1.2 Purpose and scope of this document.....	6
2 Dissemination Plan overview	7
3 Project logo	9
4 Online media	10
4.1 Website	10
4.1.1 General overview	10
4.1.2 Blog.....	11
4.1.3 Live Stream	11
4.2 Newsletter (Press Release).....	11
4.3 Social media.....	11
5 Print media	13
5.1 Poster and flyer	13
5.2 Marketing business cards.....	13
6 Conferences, workshops, trade fairs and exhibitions	14
6.1 Conferences and workshops	14
6.2 Trade fairs and exhibitions	14
7 Project documentation and publications	15
7.1 Project reports.....	15
7.2 Scientific publications.....	15
7.3 Scientific datasets.....	15
8 Educational outreach	16
8.1 Lecture material	16
8.2 Antarctic seed campaign	16
8.3 Experiment Toolkit	16
9 Press interaction	17
9.1 Official press releases.....	17
9.2 Press articles.....	18
9.3 Documentaries	19
10 Video documentation and animations	20
10.1 Animation	20
11 Summary	21
References	22

Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AD	Applicable Document	IAC	International Astronautical Congress
AIAA	American Institute of Aeronautics	ICES	International Conference on Environmental Systems
AS	Aero Sekur S.p.A.	IP	Intellectual Property
AST	Airbus Defence and Space	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research	ISS	International Space Station
BLSS	Bio-regenerative Life Support Systems	ISLWG	Information Systems Liaison Working Group
CEA	Controlled Environment Agriculture	ICES	International Conference on Environmental Systems
CNR	National Research Council	LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology
COSPAR	Committee on Space Research	LSG	LIQUIFER Systems Group
D	Deliverable	M#	Month Number
DLO	Wageningen University and Research	PP	Program Participants
DLR	German Aerospace Center	RD	Reference Document
DLR-RY	German Aerospace Center - Institute of Space Systems	R&D	Research & Development
EC	European Commission	SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
EDEN	Evolution and Design of Environmentally-Closed Nutrition-Sources	TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A.
ES	EnginSoft S.p.A.	TBD	To Be Determined
ESA	European Space Agency	TPZ	Telespazio S.p.A.
EU	European Union	UoG	University of Guelph
HS	Heliospectra AB	WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 *Overall Objectives of the EDEN ISS Project*

The EDEN ISS project is interested in promoting its progress in space greenhouse research to the scientific community and to the general public as to ensure continuation of project objectives. The (ultimate) goal of the EDEN ISS project is to further advance controlled environment agriculture technologies for safe food production on-board the International Space Station (ISS) and other planetary outposts.

Through the complete transparency and distribution of project results to researchers and the proactive educational school program that will be designed for students within the EU and Canada, EDEN ISS is interested and committed to creating awareness and excitement regarding the future of human space exploration.

A critical component of future, human space exploration will be the supply of edible food. The development of innovations associated with cultivating food in closed-loop systems is an integral part of a sustainable human presence in space. EDEN ISS will develop an advanced nutrient delivery system, a high performance LED lighting systems, a bio-detection and decontamination systems and food quality and safety procedures and technologies.

Distribution of the project results to interested parties guarantees an impact to the European economy and enhances the spin-off potential of these validated technologies.

Furthermore, EDEN ISS will study the utilization of the constructed facility for future system implementations (i.e., for other environments/applications), of which results will be made public.

1.2 *Purpose and scope of this document*

This document will provide a description of the various means and tools that will be used by the EDEN ISS team for outreach and dissemination purposes. The intended audience for the dissemination includes the international research community, industry, and stakeholders, students as well as the public at large.

2 Dissemination Plan overview

The dissemination of EDEN ISS project findings is an important output component of the project and hence has been given the status of a dedicated work package (WP 7.1).

The objective of the dissemination work is to ensure lasting and far-reaching impact of the EDEN ISS project results and focuses on the distribution of these results to both the general public and to the research community. EDEN ISS should attract active participation of researchers in academia, SMEs and industry and should promote European space R&D activities worldwide in order to strengthen the European position in the space technologies sector. The EDEN ISS consortium will use different means to reach as many people as possible, including the utilization of different media (e.g. online, offline), different formats (e.g. text, video, photos) and different contents (e.g. scientific, educational).

LSG will establish a website (deliverable D7.1) and formulate newsletters (deliverables D7.2-D7.5) as a means of project dissemination. These will provide general information about the project and its progress and contribute to public relations. Photos, video clips and interviews (deliverable D7.6) will be uploaded to the website, explaining the technical and scientific purpose and impact of the project. As well, the website will include a blog maintained by the expedition personnel and a live stream from Antarctica. Furthermore, the project will be actively promoted in social media. More details about the website can be found in Chapter 4.

The consortium will also utilize print media. Here the EDEN ISS team will focus on posters and flyers with varied content and for various occasions. Marketing business cards will be used to promote the website. Detailed information can be found in Chapter 5.

Chapter 6 describes the promotion of EDEN ISS at conferences, trade fairs and exhibitions.

The EDEN ISS consortium agrees with the European Commission's vision on open access for publicly funded scientific information. Therefore, only the most essential project reports are considered confidential. All remaining reports and scientific publications and data will be made available to the scientific community, more information can be found in Chapter 7.

During the project, a number of actions will be established to strengthen the educational training in related fields (e.g. biology, horticulture). LSG will develop a package of teaching material (deliverable D7.7) targeted for both teachers and students that will discuss the main topics explored within EDEN ISS. Furthermore, an experiment toolkit (deliverable D7.8) will be developed and made available to interested parties. The toolkit will represent a small growth chamber that can be used to conduct simple plant growth experiments. The EDEN ISS consortium will also establish an Antarctic seed campaign. The educational outreach is described in detail in Chapter 8.

Chapter 9 describes the planned interaction with the press and what actions are planned or already in place to raise the interest of the press.

A documentary movie is also envisioned for the project, which should highlight the complete process of the project and especially the field campaign in Antarctica.

Figure 2-1 presents the top-level dissemination timeline of the EDEN ISS project.

3 Project logo

Under the leadership of DLR, a logo design contest was conducted in order to receive a large number of possible designs. DLR selected three finalists and the consortium voted during the kick-off meeting to determine the winning design. Figure 3-1 shows the final logo.

The graphic represents the plant cultivation campaign that will occur at Neumayer Station III in Antarctica and the future of such developments that applicable to the International Space Station, and as a long-term goal, on the Moon and Mars.

Figure 3-1: EDEN ISS logo

4 Online media

The long-term objective is to create a community of interested parties with a focus on human space-flight and exploration, bio-regenerative life support systems (BLSS), space greenhouses, terrestrial applications and to foster the awareness for sustainable living on Earth. Public participation will be solicited via carefully selected channels – both online and offline. It is our intention that our presence in social and professional networking sites will have great potential in reaching the general public; those directly interested in space related research as well as those who are only curious.

4.1 Website

4.1.1 General overview

A dedicated website (www.eden-iss.net) will be maintained throughout the project duration by LSG, with active contribution by all partners. The project website is well designed, interactive and user-friendly (front-end).

It has been designed to incorporate dynamic text that enables easy access to the site and its contents from various sized electronic devices. Three featured images serve as the homepage’s public face and serve as ‘windows’ into the project. The website was designed to permit multiple ways of experiencing the site, allowing the visitor to explore the contents at various degrees of depth. A visitor will have an idea of what the EDEN ISS project entails at the first instance upon entering the website. Further exploration of the website contents will provide a more thorough background. The featured images will be exchanged intermittently – to give the website an ‘active’ presence on-line.

The website provides a project introduction and overview and a profile for each consortium member. It will serve as a platform for posting relevant news about and associated with the EDEN ISS project and most importantly, it will provide information on the project’s development. It will feature a dynamic ‘gallery space’ which will provide milestone results, photos, video animation clips, podcasts and personnel interviews. Highlighted on the website will be a blog maintained by DLR and live video streaming from Antarctica which are both discussed in the following subchapters. The website will also have a link to the repository storing open-access, peer-reviewed publications (conference proceedings, journal papers, etc.) and downloadable datasets. Additional components of the website include a section devoted to downloadable educational information packets.

The website will be optimized to facilitate its appearance in search engine results.

Figure 4-1: A screenshot of the EDEN ISS website (www.eden-iss.net) under development

4.1.2 Blog

The EDEN ISS project will support a blog on the project website that is regularly updated by DLR and invited guest authors. The first blog posts will be posted shortly after the launch of the website. The blog intends to give the project a human side. Complementary to the general project information provided on the website, the blog will give insight behind the scene of a European research projects. The blog will also be used to illustrate the preparation and execution of the Antarctic research campaign. Guest authors (from the consortium and also externals) will be invited to write articles for the blog for specific topics (e.g. scientific, educational and informational).

As a marketing idea of the project it is visualized that the DLR personnel conducting the year-long research campaign in Antarctica will be featured as a real-live-person, conducting real-live-coverage in one of the most remote and extreme environments on Earth. It is intended that the DLR personnel has a face and a name and is able to communicate directly with both the public and with classrooms worldwide.

4.1.3 Live Stream

During the Antarctic deployment at the Neumayer III a live video stream will be a highlight of the website. The analogue test mission will be on view in a format showing the overall test facility in its entirety as well as through several close-up views of specific plant trays. Live chats with the expedition personnel will occur periodically. The live stream will be visible on the project website.

4.2 Newsletter (Press Release)

Four newsletters (see 9.1 Official press releases) will also serve as ‘Official Press Releases’ and will be published and disseminated over the course of the project. Each of them will describe, in a visually attractive and generally understandable manner, the objectives and approaches taken by the EDEN ISS project. They will give updates on project outcomes and events (e.g. workshops, conferences). They will list contact information and general information about the consortium and the funding agency. These newsletters will also serve as PR for the various agencies and will be sent out to respective press agencies.

Newsletter #1 was completed in April 2015 and in conjunction served also as the project’s first ‘Press Release’. It described the goals of the projects and the general topics that will be explored by the EDEN ISS team.

Table 4-1: Newsletter schedule

Newsletter No.	Timing when the newsletter is scheduled to be published	Deliverable No.
Newsletter #1	First press release and published 10.4.2015.	D7.2
Newsletter #2	Will be published in month 15.	D7.3
Newsletter #3	Will be published in month 25.	D7.4
Newsletter #4	Will be published in month 35.	D7.5

4.3 Social media

Major project highlights as well as general descriptions will be shared via a Facebook profile. Documentaries about the EDEN ISS project will be uploaded to youtube.com and vimeo.com as they are created. A Twitter profile featuring the mobile test facility (similar to those created for the Mars rover Curiosity) will be established to post status information in a narrative way. Researchers from the

consortium will use their profiles on researchgate.net, academia.edu, etc. to disseminate project results and to promote the project.

5 Print media

Additional supporting tools such as posters, flyers and marketing business cards will facilitate the dissemination goals of the EDEN ISS project. LSG will be supported by all project partners in the design and development of the posters and flyers and in determining their content. These will be disseminated to the press, the scientific community, the EU and the public via diverse channels.

5.1 Poster and flyer

Partners will design and organize posters and flyers as necessary for conferences and/or for educational purposes. A general project flyer will be created by LSG and made available to the consortium.

5.2 Marketing business cards

The EDEN ISS project will utilize marketing business cards to promote the website, the Facebook profile and the Twitter account. Marketing business cards are an innovative way of promotion, because the promoter can give a small takeaway to interested people. This increases the chance that people will remember the project when they are back home and lead to visiting the EDEN ISS website. The EDEN ISS marketing business card will feature the project name, logo and a motto on the front side of the card and a call to visit the website and to follow the project's social media profiles on the back side. The marketing business cards will be designed and made available to the consortium by LSG.

6 Conferences, workshops, trade fairs and exhibitions

6.1 Conferences and workshops

It is expected that consortium partners will attend international workshops and conferences in order to disseminate information on the project goals and achievements. LSG, with help from the other consortium partners will also prepare a public presentation and assure ad-hoc support to Horizon 2020 coordinators in its communication with the specialized press or scientific community on the outcomes of the project. As of now, the following conferences and workshops are on the EDEN ISS target list:

Table 6-1: List of target conferences and workshops

Conference/workshop name	Date	Location
International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)	July 12-16, 2015 July 2016 <i>[annually]</i>	Bellevue, WA, USA Vienna, Austria
International Astronautical Congress (IAC)	October 12-16, 2015 October 2016 October 2017 <i>[annually]</i>	Jerusalem, Israel Guadalajara, Mexico Adelaide, Australia
Agrospace Conference	May 2016 May 2018 <i>[bi-annually]</i>	Sperlonga, Italy Sperlonga, Italy
ISLWG Workshop bio-regenerative life support	May 18-19, 2015	Torino, Italy
Committee on Space Research (COSPAR)	July 30 - Aug. 7, 2016 July 14-22, 2018 <i>[bi-annually]</i>	Istanbul, Turkey Pasadena, CA, USA
AIAA Space and Astronautics Forum and Exposition (AIAA SPACE)	Aug. 31 - Sep. 2, 2015 Sep. 12-15, 2016 <i>[annually]</i>	Pasadena, CA, USA Long Beach, CA, USA

The list of conferences here is just indicative, not exhaustive. More conferences will be added as the project progresses. DLR with assistance of LSG will track the participation of EDEN ISS consortium members at conferences for evaluation.

6.2 Trade fairs and exhibitions

It is expected that consortium partners will attend international trade fairs in order to disseminate information on the project goals and achievements. DLR with assistance of LSG will track the participation of EDEN ISS consortium members at trade fairs for evaluation.

7 Project documentation and publications

Open access to publications accelerates the research and discovery process, leading to increased returns in investments provided by the European Commission and avoidance of the duplication of research efforts. Furthermore, open access facilitates enhanced opportunities for multi-disciplinary research, as well as inter-institutional and inter-sectorial collaborations, such as the proposed EDEN ISS project.

According to Horizon2020 rules; project documentation, publications and datasets are to be stored in an independent online repository. For more information please see the Data Management Plan (D1.2).

7.1 Project reports

Almost all project documentations (e.g. reports, plans) are classified as 'Public' and will be made available to the scientific community. A high-quality yearly project report will be compiled by the consortium highlighting the achievements of the past year and will provide an outlook on the coming year.

7.2 Scientific publications

Papers will be regularly prepared (written) by individual consortium members and are important criteria for conferences. It is a goal of EDEN ISS to make the EDEN ISS project accessible to many target groups including universities, industries, and the European Space Agency (ESA).

All consortium partners will publish key technical and scientific results on international conferences, workshops and journals. Publications will be reviewed and authorized by the Management Board after considering the effect on the established IPR. The Scientific Advisory Board will support the promotion and publication activities. Main targets are specialized journals and magazines in aerospace engineering, closed environment agriculture, life support systems, horticulture and biology/medicine.

All scientific publications related to EDEN ISS will be made available through the repository and scientific social media networks.

7.3 Scientific datasets

EDEN ISS intends to offer the scientific community, outside of the official consortium partners, the opportunity to benefit from its research by supplying raw data sets generated through the experimentation processes in the labs both in Bremen and in Antarctica.

For the scientific community, access to certain unprocessed mobile test facility metadata will be made available in a near real-time basis. It will be archived online at a repository and be made available on a non-discriminatory basis, with as few restrictions as possible. The data recorded throughout the project is described in detail in the Data Management Plan (deliverable D1.2).

8 Educational outreach

EDEN ISS plans to engage the next generation of space explorers through an educational outreach program that will offer to teachers and pupils information and activities related to the cultivation of plants for the purpose of growing food in space, either on the International Space Station or further destinations like the Moon and Mars.

8.1 Lecture material

The first component is high quality lecture material for schools (age range between 6 and 12 years) and universities (with main input from the EDEN ISS research institution partners) made available, free of cost, upon the request of teachers and/or professors within EU member states and Canada. It will offer information and suggest activities in the topics of space, biology, and growing food under specific environmental conditions appropriate to learning abilities.

8.2 Antarctic seed campaign

The Antarctic seed campaign is the second component of the educational program of EDEN ISS. DLR personnel will take a number of seeds to the Neumayer III station. These seeds will be brought back to Europe after they have stayed in Antarctica for a number of weeks. The seeds will then be made available to classrooms in Europe and Canada. These will also be included in the Experiment Toolkit.

8.3 Experiment Toolkit

The third component of the educational outreach program is the distribution of 'plant growth experiment tool kits' (deliverable D7.8) to a select group of classrooms throughout EU member states and Canada. The kits will be developed by DLR and will highlight the key issues of Controlled Environment Agriculture (CEA) technologies and different growth procedures related to cultivating plants in space. Here, the pupils can learn different aspects about BLSS and the role of higher plants in human space exploration endeavors. Seeds from the Antarctic seed campaign will be included in the Experiment toolkit. Additionally, a construction manual and a do-it-yourself video will be made available for everybody through the website.

9 Press interaction

Press releases and press coverage in relevant publications across the European Union and in other countries will facilitate EDEN ISS's dissemination goals.

9.1 Official press releases

Press releases will be disseminated throughout the project to mark significant project milestones. All Newsletters are intended to become Press Releases (see also Section 4.2). Figure 9-1 and Figure 9-2 show the press release that was distributed by the EDEN ISS consortium following the project kick-off meeting that took place in Bremen on 5.3.2015. Dated 10.4.2015, it was released in German and in English. Individual project members also translated it into their native languages. It was titled: "EDEN ISS – growing food for space exploration."

EDEN ISS – growing food for space exploration

A new project is underway under the European Union's *Research and Innovation Action* program Horizon 2020, within the topic of 'Space exploration / Life support.' Thirteen international organizations, including universities, corporations and small businesses, in the cross-disciplinary fields of food growth, life support, engineering and design come together in taking one step further towards the independent exploration in worlds unknown such as the Moon or Mars. During the four year project, they will collaboratively develop innovations in cultivating food in closed-loop systems.

EDEN ISS is a project focused on the '*Ground Demonstration of Plant Cultivation Technologies and - Operation in Space*' and the enhancement of those technologies, '*For Safe Food Production on-board the International Space Station (ISS) and Future Human Space Exploration Vehicles and Planetary Outposts.*'

The consortium is led by the German Aerospace Center (DLR) Institute of Space Systems in Bremen, Germany and includes the following partners;

EDEN ISS team photo, Credit: DLR 2015

- DLR Institute of Aerospace Medicine in Cologne, Germany
- LIQUIFER Systems Group, Austria
- National Research Council, Italy
- University of Guelph, Canada
- Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Germany
- Enginsoft S.p.A., Italy
- Airbus Defense and Space, Germany
- Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A., Italy
- Aero Sekur S.p.A., Italy
- Wageningen University and Research, the Netherlands
- Heliospectra AB, Sweden
- Limerick Institute of Technology, Ireland
- Telespazio S.p.A., Italy

The overall goal of the EDEN ISS project is to further advance key controlled environment agriculture technologies beyond the state-of-the-art, including; an advanced nutrient delivery system, a high performance LED lighting system, a bio-detection and decontamination system and food quality and safety procedures and technologies.

Figure 9-1: Press Release of project EDEN ISS 'kick-off' (page 1)

Credit: DLR

A mobile container-sized greenhouse test facility will be built to demonstrate and validate different key technologies and procedures necessary for safe food production within a (semi-) closed system.

The test facility will be designed to fit into standardized shipping containers and will consist of three essential 'parts.'

The *service section* will house the main support subsystems, including; thermal, power, air ventilation and nutrient/water subsystems and will provide working space for pre- and harvest procedures. The *International Standard Payload Rack (ISPR)* section will contain two rack systems for plant production (similar to the rack-type used on the ISS) and the *Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG)* will consist of a highly adaptable multi-shelf growth system, capable of maintaining a number of different environmental settings.

Credit: LIQUIFER Systems Group 2015

The plant cultivation technologies will first be tested in a laboratory setting at the sites of the consortium partners. All systems will be integrated at DLR in Bremen, followed by an extensive test period. In October 2017, the complete facility will be shipped to the German Neumayer III station in Antarctica. The station is operated by the Alfred-Wegener-Institute and has unique capabilities and infrastructure for testing plant cultivation under extreme environmental and logistical conditions. It is foreseen that the container-sized greenhouse of the EDEN ISS project will provide year-round fresh food supplementation for the Neumayer Station III crew.

Figure 9-2: Press Release of project EDEN ISS 'kick-off' (page 2)

9.2 Press articles

EDEN ISS has already been covered in the press. Presented below is a list of other selected press articles that have already been published. The EDEN ISS team shall endeavor to widen the press coverage further in the weeks and months ahead.

Table 9-1: Press coverage for EDEN ISS kick-off

Press/Publication Article Title	URL
EDEN ISS – growing food for space exploration	http://www.ces.uoguelph.ca/news/EDEN_ISS_PressRelease_2015_03_30.pdf
EDEN ISS – growing food for space exploration	http://www.heliospectra.com/blog/heliospectra-joins-germanys-eden-initiative-developing-safe-space-station-food-crops
Heliospectra Joins Germany's Eden Initiative For Developing Safe Space Station Food Crops - WILL	http://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/heliospectra-joins-germanys-eden-initiative-for-developing-safe-space-station-food-crops-277561041.html

PROVIDE LED LIGHTING SYSTEMS FOR PLANTS GROWN IN CLOSED ENVIRONMENTS	
LETTUCE ENTERTAIN YOU – IN SPACE!	https://www.thalesgroup.com/en/worldwide/space/case-study/lettuce-entertain-you-space

The list of articles here is just indicative, not exhaustive. DLR with assistance of LSG will track press articles related to EDEN ISS for evaluation.

9.3 Documentaries

Throughout the duration of the EDEN ISS project, small documentary footage will be accumulated illustrating the progress of the experimentations. This documentation can be derived from third parties.

DLR has established a close collaboration with the German online scientific magazine ‘Substanz.’ Substanz journalists have already visited DLR’s EDEN laboratory three times to make interviews, photos and videos. The magazine will follow the development of DLR’s EDEN research group in general and especially the EDEN ISS project. The coverage includes a series of articles featuring video and text articles. More articles will be published on a regular basis as the project develops. The link to the latest article is: <http://www.substanzmagazin.de/weltraumgemuese/>. Figure 9-3 shows a screenshot of the article that includes an introductory video.

Vom Gartenbaumarkt auf die Internationale Raumstation: Bremer Ingenieure entwickeln ein Gewächshaus, das Astronauten mit frischem Gemüse versorgen soll. Das ehrgeizige DLR-Projekt Eden wird ihnen in den nächsten Jahren viel Geduld und Nervenstärke abverlangen. Den Forscheralltag mit all seinen Höhen und Tiefen begleiten wir in unserer neuen Rubrik "Forschung in Echtzeit".

Figure 9-3: Screenshot of article and short documentary at ‘Substanz Wissenschaftsmagazin’

The EDEN ISS consortium will establish more collaboration with journalists throughout the project to facilitate more documentaries.

10 Video documentation and animations

The EDEN ISS consortium anticipates the production of a professional documentary. It is conceived that a well-known broadcasting company(s) would be interested in documenting the process of design and manufacturing of the mobile test facility and capture the importance of the analogue campaign at Antarctica. For this task, contact will be made with professional documentary production companies and TV channels (e.g. BBC Horizon, Discovery Channel, National Geographic).

10.1 Animation

A professional animation of the mobile test facility will be produced by LSG. The animation will be used to explain the functionality of the facility and how the different systems interact with each other to grow plants.

11 Summary

The Dissemination Plan describes the outreach and dissemination goals of EDEN ISS and the future work carried out within WP 7.1 of the project. As outlined in this document, consortium partners will be using a variety of means and tools to achieve these goals. The EDEN ISS team will also endeavor to find synergies with other EU-funded projects. All consortium partners will provide information about their respective part of the project to foster public engagement.

The overall goal is to educate, inspire and enlighten the target audience about the possibilities of growing food in space. Achieving this goal will ultimately not only pave the way for sustainable food growth on Earth but also expand possibilities of human exploration beyond Earth orbit.

References

None